

Gazania ciliaris Treasure Flower

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© R. McKenzie

Group: Eudicot

Size: 0.1 - 0.2 m (height)

Distribution:

South Africa: Western Cape and Eastern Cape

Importance:

Gazania is a floristically important indigenous genus distributed throughout South Africa but with its centre of diversity in the Cape floristic region. *Gazania* hybrids are globally important in horticulture. *Gazania ciliaris* is a Cape-endemic species and diverged early during diversification of the genus. Thus, it is crucial for exploring the genetic diversity, evolution, cytology and biogeography of *Gazania*.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 114.5 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 20.54 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 6.43 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 0.7%, Duplicated: 98.8%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 457.91 kilobases

Contig number: 22 796

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Date Published: 2025-10-28

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416229>

